

On Rough Statistical Convergence in Neutrosophic Normed Spaces

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Abstract. In this paper, we have presented rough statistical convergence of sequence on neutrosophic normed spaces as an important convergence criterion. As neutrosophication can handle partially dependent components, partially independent components and even independent components involved in real-world problems. By examining some properties related to rough convergence in these spaces we provide some useful functional tools in the situations of inconsistency and indeterminacy in the real world. Further, we have established some equivalent conditions on the set of statistical limit points as well as on the set of cluster points in these spaces for rough statistically convergent sequences.

Keywords: Neutrosophic normed space; statistical convergence; rough convergence, rough statistical convergence

1. Introduction

It has been seen that new quests are revealing in the real-life problems with time. So many methods are already existing, and researchers are still investigating new variants for existing and future problems. In modern logic, the three-way decision situations like from accepting/rejecting/pending, from yes/no/not-applicable, from sports win/lose/tie etc. the standard analysis is not sufficient, which leads to employ non-standard analysis. Smarandache [36–38] provided neutrosophic sets with regard to the powerful advancement of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets, that established the concept for the classic sets, fuzzy sets, vague sets etc., for non-standard analysis. The conception of neutrosophic set can manage the indeterminate data of the problem whereas the impression of fuzzy set theory as well as intuitionistic fuzzy set theory are not able to provide solution when the relation is indeterminate. Neutrosophic sets are

providing the ideas to solve real-life situations where indeterminacy occurs like Databases [4], Image processing problems [15], Control theory [1], Medical diagnosis problems [2], Decision making problems [19], and so on.

As every element of the neutrosophic set has a truth value, a false value and an indeterminacy value respectively, which lies in the non-standard unit interval. Due to this nature neutrosophic is more adjustable and efficient tool because of its ability to handle, not only the free components of information but also partially independent and dependent information. In neutrosophic set elements may have inconsistent information (*i.e.* sum of the components > 1) or incomplete information (*i.e.* sum of the components < 1) or consistent information (*i.e.* sum of the components $= 1$), and other interval-valued components (*i.e.* without any restriction on the sum of superior or inferior components).

Definition 1.1. [36] Let U be a subset of \mathbb{X} (which is space of points) with $a \in \mathbb{X}$. Then set U with $\tau(a)$, $v(a)$ and $\eta(a)$ in \mathbb{X} is called neutrosophic set(NS) and expressed as

$$U = \{ \langle a, \tau(a), v(a), \eta(a) \rangle : a \in \mathbb{X}, \tau(a), v(a), \eta(a) \in I \}$$

where $\tau(a)$, $v(a)$ and $\eta(a)$ denotes truth membership, indeterminacy membership and falsity membership functions respectively such that $0^- \leq \tau(a) + v(a) + \eta(a) \leq 3^+$. Also $I =]0^-, 1^+[$ represents some non-standard unit interval.

However, Wang et al. [41] and Ye [42] have customized the existing definition for neutrosophic sets by suggesting the structure of single-valued neutrosophic sets and simplified neutrosophic sets respectively using the interval $[0, 1]$, that can be utilized in engineering and scientific applications.

Later, Mahapatra and Bera [9] studied the notion of neutrosophic soft linear spaces. Kirişçi and Şimşek [20] has introduced neutrosophic metric spaces and established its basic characteristic properties like open ball, compactness, completeness and nowhere dense. Further, Kirişçi and Şimşek [21] presented the idea of neutrosophic normed spaces as a notable consideration of neutrosophic metric spaces. Further, required basic terms related to neutrosophic normed spaces are elaborated as below:

Definition 1.2. [35] A continuous t-norm is the mapping $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

- (i) \otimes is continuous, associative, commutative and with identity 1,
- (ii) $a_1 \otimes b_1 \leq a_2 \otimes b_2$ whenever $a_1 \leq a_2$ and $b_1 \leq b_2$, for $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 1.3. [35] A continuous t-conorm is the mapping $\odot : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that

- (i) \odot is continuous, associative, commutative and with identity 0,
- (ii) $a_1 \odot b_1 \leq a_2 \odot b_2$ whenever $a_1 \leq a_2$ and $b_1 \leq b_2$, for $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 1.4. [21] A neutrosophic normed space(NNS) is 4-tuple $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ with vector space \mathbb{X} , continuous t-norm \otimes , continuous t-conorm \odot and normed space $\mathfrak{N} = \{ \langle \tau(a), v(a), \eta(a) \rangle : a \in \mathbb{X} \}$ such that $\mathfrak{N} : \mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow [0, 1]$, if for each $x, y \in \mathbb{X}$ and $s, t > 0$, we have

- (i) $0 \leq \tau(x, t), v(x, t), \eta(x, t) \leq 1$,
- (ii) $\tau(x, t) + v(x, t) + \eta(x, t) \leq 3$,
- (iii) $\tau(x, t) = 1, v(x, t) = 0$ and $\eta(x, t) = 0$ for $t > 0$ iff $x = 0$,
- (iv) $\tau(x, t) = 0, v(x, t) = 1$ and $\eta(x, t) = 1$ for $t \leq 0$,
- (v) $\tau(\alpha x, t) = \tau\left(x, \frac{t}{|\alpha|}\right), v(\alpha x, t) = v\left(x, \frac{t}{|\alpha|}\right)$ and $\eta(\alpha x, t) = \eta\left(x, \frac{t}{|\alpha|}\right)$ for $\alpha \neq 0$,
- (vi) $\tau(x, \circ)$ is continuous non-decreasing function,
- (vii) $\tau(x, s) \otimes \tau(x, t) \leq \tau(x + y, s + t)$,
- (viii) $v(x, \circ)$ is continuous non-increasing function,
- (ix) $v(x, s) \odot v(y, t) \geq v(x + y, s + t)$,
- (x) $\eta(x, \circ)$ is continuous non-increasing function,
- (xi) $\eta(x, s) \odot \eta(y, t) \geq \eta(x + y, s + t)$,
- (xii) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \tau(x, t) = 1, \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} v(x, t) = 0$ and $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \eta(x, t) = 0$.

Then (τ, v, η) is known as neutrosophic norm.

Example 1.5. [21] Let $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$ be any normed space. For every $t > 0$ and all $x \in \mathbb{X}$, take

- (i) $\tau(x, t) = \frac{t}{t + \|x\|}, v(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t + \|x\|}$ and $\eta(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t}$ when $t > \|x\|$,
- (ii) $\tau(x, t) = 0, v(x, t) = 1$ and $\eta(x, t) = 1$ when $t \leq \|x\|$.

Also, $a \otimes b = ab$ and $a \odot b = a + b - ab \forall a, b \in [0, 1]$.

Then, 4-tuple $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ is a NNS which satisfies above mentioned conditions.

A generalized version of intuitionistic fuzzy norms is considered in neutrosophic normed spaces that help to explore the basic properties like convergence and completeness in such spaces using continuous and bounded linear operators. Omran and Elrawy [30] have discussed the continuous operators along with bounded operators in the setting of neutrosophic normed spaces. Also, Khan and Khan [16] studied the various topological characterization of such spaces. Further, Kirişci and Şimşek [21] have established sequence convergence on neutrosophic normed spaces as given below.

Definition 1.6. [21] Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS with neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) . A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in \mathbb{X} is called convergent to $\xi \in X$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$ we can find $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ provided $\tau(x_k - \xi, t) > 1 - \epsilon, v(x_k - \xi, t) < \epsilon$ and $\eta(x_k - \xi, t) < \epsilon$ for $k \geq k_0$. It is convenient to represent symbolically by $(\tau, v, \eta)\text{-}\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x_k = \xi$ or $x_k \xrightarrow{(\tau, v, \eta)} \xi$.

Remark 1.7. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$ be any normed space. For every $t > 0$ and all $x \in \mathbb{X}$, take

$$(i) \tau(x, t) = \frac{t}{t + \|x\|}, \quad v(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t + \|x\|} \text{ and } \eta(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t} \text{ when } t > \|x\|,$$

$$(ii) \tau(x, t) = 0, \quad v(x, t) = 1 \text{ and } \eta(x, t) = 1 \text{ when } t \leq \|x\|.$$

Also, $a \otimes b = ab$ and $a \odot b = a + b - ab \forall a, b \in [0, 1]$.

Then, 4-tuple $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ is a NNS.

Also, $x_k \xrightarrow{(\tau, v, \eta)} x$ if and only if $x_k \xrightarrow{\|\cdot\|} x$.

Also Kirişci and Şimşek [21] have established the statistical convergence for sequences on neutrosophic normed spaces with natural density. Although, natural density of set A , where $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, has given by $\delta(A) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} |\{a \leq n : a \in A\}|$, provided limit exists, where $|\cdot|$ designates the order of the enclosed set. Further, sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ converges statistically to ξ , if $A(\epsilon) = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : |x_k - \xi| > \epsilon\}$ has zero natural density (see [14]).

Definition 1.8. [21] Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS with neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) . A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in \mathbb{X} is called statistically convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$, we have

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi, t) \leq 1 - \epsilon \text{ or } v(x_k - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon, \eta(x_k - \xi, t) \geq \epsilon\}) = 0.$$

It is convenient to represent symbolically by $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x_k = \xi$ or $x_k \xrightarrow{St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}} \xi$.

Some remarkable results on the theory of neutrosophic normed spaces and statistical convergence on the framework of neutrosophic normed spaces have been studied in different aspects (*c.f.* [8, 10, 16–18, 22, 23, 23, 25, 34, 39]). This convergence concept can also be further studied in different directions as this theory has a basic function in so many areas of mathematics, economics, science and technology. In this paper we associate this theory with the rough convergence of sequences.

The concept of rough convergence deals with the approximate solution of any real-life situation from the numerical point of view. It helps to verify the correctness of solutions obtained from the computer programs and to draw conclusions from scientific experiments. The rough convergence has been initially introduced by Phu [32] as an interesting generalization of usual convergence for the sequences on finite-dimensional normed linear spaces, and later suggested on infinite-dimensional normed linear spaces [33]. Apart from defining the idea of rough convergence, he also contributed towards the properties like closeness and convexity of the rough limit set.

Definition 1.9. [32] A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in a normed linear space $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$ is called rough convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ for some non-negative number r if for every $\epsilon > 0$ we can find $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ provided $\|x_k - \xi\| < r + \epsilon$ for $k \geq k_0$.

Aytar [6] developed the extensive notion of rough convergence by applying the statistical analogue about this concept as rough statistical convergence for the sequences, like usual convergence is continued to statistical convergence for sequences using natural density by Fast [13]. Moreover, Aytar [7] also examined some criteria related to convexity and closeness associated with the set of rough statistical limit points. In fact, he established some properties related to this set with the set of rough cluster points.

Definition 1.10. [6] A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in any normed linear space $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$ is called rough statistically convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ for some non-negative number r if for every $\epsilon > 0$ we get

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \|x_k - \xi\| \geq r + \epsilon\}) = 0,$$

and ξ is identified as r -*St*-limit of sequence $x = \{x_k\}$.

In the literature, during last few years, considerable progress is going on the field of rough convergence (*c.f.* [3, 5, 11, 12, 24, 26–29, 31]) in different aspects which leads us to investigate and explore rough statistical convergence on the theory of neutrosophic normed spaces. The significance of introducing rough convergence in this structure is to obtain an efficient tool of convergence for acting on various types of uncertainties and imprecision unified in real-life systems.

2. Main Results

We first mention the conception of rough statistical convergence of sequences on neutrosophic normed spaces that will be helpful in studying the major results of our work.

Definition 2.1. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS with neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) . A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in \mathbb{X} is said to be rough convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) for some non-negative number r if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we can find $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ provided

$$\tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda, \nu(x_k - \xi, t) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \xi, t) < \lambda \text{ for } k \geq k_0.$$

It is convenient to represent symbolically by $r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x_k = \xi$ or $x_k \xrightarrow{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \xi$.

Definition 2.2. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS with neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) . A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in \mathbb{X} is said to be rough statistically convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) for some non-negative number r if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$,

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } \nu(x_k - \xi, r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k - \xi, r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda\}) = 0.$$

It is convenient to represent symbolically by $r\text{-}St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)} - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} x_k = \xi$ or $x_k \xrightarrow{r\text{-}St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \xi$.

Remark 2.3. For $r = 0$, the impression of rough statistical convergence due to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) agrees with the impression of statistical convergence due to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$.

The r - $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}$ -limit of a sequence may be not unique. Therefore, we take into consideration r - $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}$ -limit set of sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ as $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \{\xi : x_k \xrightarrow{r-St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \xi\}$. Moreover, sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ is $r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}$ -convergent if $LIM_x^{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \neq \phi$ where $LIM_x^{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} = \{\xi^* \in \mathbb{X} : x_k \xrightarrow{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \xi^*\}$. For unbounded sequence $LIM_x^{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}}$ is always empty.

But in rough statistical convergence on a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$, we may have $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \neq \phi$ for unbounded sequence. To justify this the next example is given.

Example 2.4. Consider any real normed space $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$. For every $t > 0$ and all $x \in \mathbb{X}$, take

(i) $\tau(x, t) = \frac{t}{t+\|x\|}$, $\nu(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t+\|x\|}$ and $\nu(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t}$ when $t > \|x\|$,

(ii) $\tau(x, t) = 0$, $\nu(x, t) = 1$ and $\nu(x, t) = 1$ when $t \leq \|x\|$.

Also, $a \otimes b = ab$ and $a \odot b = a + b - ab \forall a, b \in [0, 1]$. Then, 4-tuple $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ is a NNS.

Define a sequence

$$x_k = \begin{cases} (-1)^k & k \neq n^2 \\ k & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then

$$St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \begin{cases} \phi & r < 1 \\ [1 - r, r - 1] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

and $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \phi$ for all $r \geq 0$. Thus, this sequence is divergent in ordinary sense being unbounded. Also, this sequence is not rough convergent in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ for any r .

If $x' = \{x_{k_i}\}$ be a sub-sequence of $x = \{x_k\}$ in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ then $LIM_{x_k}^{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \subset LIM_{x_{k_i}}^{r_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}}$. But this fact fails to hold in case of rough statistical convergence. This can be justified with the next given example.

Example 2.5. Consider any real normed space $(\mathbb{X}, \|\cdot\|)$. For every $t > 0$ and all $x \in \mathbb{X}$, take

(i) $\tau(x, t) = \frac{t}{t+\|x\|}$, $\nu(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t+\|x\|}$ and $\nu(x, t) = \frac{\|x\|}{t}$ when $t > \|x\|$,

(ii) $\tau(x, t) = 0$, $\nu(x, t) = 1$ and $\nu(x, t) = 1$ when $t \leq \|x\|$.

Also, $a \otimes b = ab$ and $a \odot b = a + b - ab \forall a, b \in [0, 1]$. Then, 4-tuple $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ is a NNS.

Also the sequence

$$x_k = \begin{cases} k & k \neq n^2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

have $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = [-r, r]$. And its sub-sequence $x' = \{1, 4, 9, \dots\}$ have $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_{x'}^r = \phi$.

But this fact is true for non-thin sub-sequences of the rough statistical convergent sequence in a NNS which is explained by the next result.

Theorem 2.6. *If $x' = \{x_{k_i}\}$ be a non-thin sub-sequence of the sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ then $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \subset St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_{x'}^r$.*

Proof. Proof of this result is trivial so we are omitting it. \square

Theorem 2.7. *The set $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ of any sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ is a closed set.*

Proof. We have nothing to prove as $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \phi$.

Let $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \neq \phi$ for some $r > 0$ and consider $y = \{y_k\}$ be a convergent sequence in $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) to $y_0 \in \mathbb{X}$.

For $t \in (0, 1)$ take $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - \lambda) \otimes (1 - \lambda) > 1 - t$ and $\lambda \odot \lambda < t$. Then for $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we get $k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\tau\left(y_k - y_0; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, \nu\left(y_k - y_0; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(y_k - y_0; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ for all } k \geq k_1.$$

Let us choose $y_m \in St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ with $m > k_1$ such that

$$\delta\left(\left\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } \nu\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \geq \lambda, \eta\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \geq \lambda\right\}\right) = 0. \tag{1}$$

For $j \in \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, \nu\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda\}$ we have $\tau\left(x_j - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, \nu\left(x_j - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(x_j - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda$.

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_j - y_0; r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau\left(x_j - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \otimes \tau\left(y_m - y_0; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &> (1 - \lambda) \otimes (1 - \lambda) \\ &> 1 - t, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(x_j - y_0; r + \epsilon) &\leq \nu\left(x_j - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \odot \nu\left(y_m - y_0; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &< \lambda \odot \lambda \\ &< t, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_j - y_0; r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta\left(x_j - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \odot \eta\left(y_m - y_0; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &< \lambda \odot \lambda \\ &< t. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $j \in \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) < t\}$.

Now we have the following inclusion

$$\begin{aligned} &\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, \nu\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda\} \\ &\subseteq \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) < t\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} & \delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) \geq t, \eta(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) \geq t\}) \\ & \leq \delta\left(\left\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \geq \lambda, \eta\left(x_k - y_m; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \geq \lambda\right\}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Using (1) we get

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) \geq t, \eta(x_k - y_0; r + \epsilon) \geq t\}) = 0$$

Therefore, $y_0 \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$. \square

In next result, we are proving the convexity for set $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$.

Theorem 2.8. *Let $x = \{x_k\}$ be any sequence in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$. Then, rough statistical limit set $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) is convex for some non-negative number r .*

Proof. Let $\xi_1, \xi_2 \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$. For the convexity of the set $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$, we have to show that $[(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2] \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ for some $\beta \in (0, 1)$.

For $t \in (0, 1)$ take $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - \lambda) \otimes (1 - \lambda) > 1 - t$ and $\lambda \odot \lambda < t$. Now for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$, we define

$$M_1 = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - \xi_1; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2(1 - \beta)}\right) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v\left(x_k - \xi_1; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2(1 - \beta)}\right) \geq \lambda, \eta\left(x_k - \xi_1; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2(1 - \beta)}\right) \geq \lambda\},$$

$$M_2 = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - \xi_2; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2\beta}\right) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v\left(x_k - \xi_2; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2\beta}\right) \geq \lambda, \eta\left(x_k - \xi_2; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2\beta}\right) \geq \lambda\}.$$

As $\xi_1, \xi_2 \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$, we have $\delta(M_1) = \delta(M_2) = 0$. For $k \in M_1^c \cap M_2^c$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_k - [(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2]; r + \epsilon) & \geq \tau((1 - \beta)(x_k - \xi_1) + \beta(x_k - \xi_2); r + \epsilon) \\ & \geq \tau\left((1 - \beta)(x_k - \xi_1); \frac{r + \epsilon}{2}\right) \otimes \tau\left(\beta(x_k - \xi_2); \frac{r + \epsilon}{2}\right) \\ & \geq \tau\left(x_k - \xi_1; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2(1 - \beta)}\right) \otimes \tau\left(x_k - \xi_2; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2\beta}\right) \\ & > (1 - \lambda) \otimes (1 - \lambda) \\ & > 1 - t, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(x_k - [(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2]; r + \epsilon) & \leq v((1 - \beta)(x_k - \xi_1) + \beta(x_k - \xi_2); r + \epsilon) \\ & \leq v\left((1 - \beta)(x_k - \xi_1); \frac{r + \epsilon}{2}\right) \odot v\left(\beta(x_k - \xi_2); \frac{r + \epsilon}{2}\right) \\ & \leq v\left(x_k - \xi_1; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2(1 - \beta)}\right) \odot v\left(x_k - \xi_2; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2\beta}\right) \\ & < \lambda \odot \lambda \\ & < t. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_k - [(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2]; r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta((1 - \beta)(x_k - \xi_1) + \beta(x_k - \xi_2); r + \epsilon) \\ &\leq \eta\left((1 - \beta)(x_k - \xi_1); \frac{r + \epsilon}{2}\right) \odot \eta\left(\beta(x_k - \xi_2); \frac{r + \epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &\leq \eta\left(x_k - \xi_1; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2(1 - \beta)}\right) \odot \eta\left(x_k - \xi_2; \frac{r + \epsilon}{2\beta}\right) \\ &< \lambda \odot \lambda \\ &< t. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we get $\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - [(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2]; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(x_k - [(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2]; r + \epsilon) \geq 1 - t, \eta(x_k - [(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2]; r + \epsilon) \geq 1 - t\}) = 0$.

Hence, $[(1 - \beta)\xi_1 + \beta\xi_2] \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ i.e. $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ is a convex set. \square

Theorem 2.9. *A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ is rough statistically convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) for some non-negative number r if a sequence $y = \{y_k\}$ exists in \mathbb{X} , which is statistically convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) and for every $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ have $\tau(x_k - y_k; r) > 1 - \lambda$, $v(x_k - y_k; r) < \lambda$ and $\eta(x_k - y_k; r) < \lambda$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Proof. Let $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. Consider $y_k \xrightarrow{St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}} \xi$ and $\tau(x_k - y_k; r) < \lambda$, $v(x_k - y_k; r) > 1 - \lambda$ and $\eta(x_k - y_k; r) > 1 - \lambda$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. For given $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ take $t \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) > 1 - \lambda$ and $\lambda \odot \lambda < t$. Define

$$A = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(y_k - \xi; \epsilon) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(y_k - \xi; \epsilon) \geq t, \eta(y_k - \xi; \epsilon) \geq t\}$$

$$B = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_k; r) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(x_k - y_k; r) \geq t, \eta(x_k - y_k; r) \geq t\}$$

Clearly, $\delta(A) = 0$ and $\delta(B) = 0$. For $k \in A^c \cap B^c$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau(x_k - y_k; r) \otimes \tau(y_k - \xi; \epsilon) \\ &> (1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) \\ &> 1 - \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) &\leq v(x_k - y_k; r) \odot v(y_k - \xi; \epsilon) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta(x_k - y_k; r) \odot \eta(y_k - \xi; \epsilon) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Then $\tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda$, $v(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda$ and $\eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda$ for all $k \in A^c \cap B^c$. This implies that $\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda\} \subseteq A \cup B$.

Then, $\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda\}) \leq \delta(A) + \delta(B)$.

Hence, we get $\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda\}) = 0$. Therefore, $x_k \xrightarrow{r-St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}} \xi$. \square

Theorem 2.10. *Let $x = \{x_k\}$ be any sequence in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$. There does not exist elements $y, z \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ for some $r > 0$ and every $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ with $\varphi(y - z; mr) \leq 1 - \lambda$ or $\vartheta(y - z; mr) \geq \lambda$ for $m > 2$.*

Proof. We prove this result by contradiction. Assume there are elements $y, z \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ such that

$$\tau(y - z; mr) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(y - z; mr) \geq \lambda, \eta(y - z; mr) \geq \lambda \text{ for } m > 2 \tag{2}$$

As $y, z \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$.

For given $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ take $t \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) > 1 - \lambda$ and $\lambda \odot \lambda < t$. Then for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $t \in (0, 1)$ we have $\delta(K_1) = \delta(K_2) = 0$ where $K_1 = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(x_k - y; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \geq t, \eta(x_k - y; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \geq t\}$ and $K_2 = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - z; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } v(x_k - z; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \geq t, \eta(x_k - z; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \geq t\}$. For $k \in K_1^c \cap K_2^c$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(y - z; 2r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau\left(x_k - z; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \otimes \tau\left(x_k - y; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &> (1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) \\ &> 1 - \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(y - z; 2r + \epsilon) &\leq v\left(x_k - z; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \odot v\left(x_k - y; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(y - z; 2r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta\left(x_k - z; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \odot \eta\left(x_k - y; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\tau(y - z; 2r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda, v(y - z; 2r + \epsilon) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(y - z; 2r + \epsilon) < \lambda. \tag{3}$$

Then, from (3) we have

$$\tau(y - z; mr) > 1 - \lambda, v(y - z; mr) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(y - z; mr) < \lambda \text{ for } m > 2.$$

which is a contradiction to (2). Therefore, there does not exist elements $y, z \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ such that $\tau(y - z; mr) \leq 1 - \lambda$ or $v(y - z; mr) \geq \lambda, \eta(y - z; mr) \geq \lambda$ for $m > 2$. \square

Now, we are giving definition of statistically bounded sequence on NNS as follows:

Definition 2.11. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS with neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) . A sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in \mathbb{X} is said to be statistically bounded with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we can find a real number $M > 0$ satisfying

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k; M) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k, M) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k, M) \geq \lambda\}) = 0.$$

In view of the above definition, we obtained the next interesting result on rough statistical convergence on NNS.

Theorem 2.12. Let $x = \{x_k\}$ be any sequence in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$. Then $x = \{x_k\}$ is statistically bounded with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) if and only if $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \neq \phi$ for some $r > 0$.

Proof. Necessary part:

Consider sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ which is statistically bounded in NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$. Then, for every $\epsilon > 0, \lambda \in (0, 1)$ and some $r > 0$ we get a real number $M > 0$ satisfying

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k; M) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k, M) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k, M) \geq \lambda\}) = 0.$$

Let $K = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k; M) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k, M) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k, M) \geq \lambda\}$.

For $k \in K^c$ we have $\tau(x_k; M) > 1 - \lambda, v(x_k, M) < \lambda$ and $\eta(x_k, M) < \lambda$.

Also

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_k; r + M) &\geq \tau(0; r) \otimes \tau(x_k; M) \\ &> 1 \otimes (1 - \lambda) \\ &= 1 - \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(x_k; r + M) &< v(0; r) \odot v(x_k; M) \\ &< 0 \odot \lambda \\ &= \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_k; r + M) &< \eta(0; r) \odot \eta(x_k; M) \\ &< 0 \odot \lambda \\ &= \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $0 \in St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r$. Therefore, $St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r \neq \phi$.

Sufficient Part:

Let $St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r \neq \phi$ for some $r > 0$. So some $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ exists such that $\xi \in St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r$. For every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we have

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda \text{ or } v(x_k - \xi, r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda, \eta(x_k - \xi, r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda\}) = 0.$$

Therefore, almost all x_k 's are contained in some ball with center ξ which implies that $x = \{x_k\}$ is statistically bounded in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$. \square

Further, we define statistical cluster point for the sequence on NNS and establish some results related to it.

Definition 2.13. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS with neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) . Then $\gamma \in \mathbb{X}$ is said to be rough statistical cluster point of sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in \mathbb{X} with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) for some non-negative number r if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$,

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda \text{ and } v(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) < \lambda, \eta(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}) > 0,$$

i.e.

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda \text{ and } v(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) < \lambda, \eta(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}) \neq 0.$$

In this case, γ is known as r - $St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}$ -cluster point of a sequence $x = \{x_k\}$.

Let $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x)$ denotes the set of all r - $St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}$ -cluster points with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) of sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$. If $r = 0$ then we get ordinary statistical cluster point with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ *i.e.* $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x) = \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x)$.

Theorem 2.14. Let $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ be a NNS. Then, $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x)$ which is the set of of all r - $St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}$ -cluster points with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, v, η) of any sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ is closed for some non-negative real number r .

Proof. (i) If $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x) = \phi$, then we have to prove nothing.

(ii) If $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x) \neq \phi$. Then, take sequence $y = \{y_k\} \subseteq \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x)$ such that $y_k \xrightarrow{(\tau,v,\eta)} y_*$. It is enough to show that $y_* \in \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x)$. Now for $t \in (0, 1)$ take $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - \lambda) \otimes (1 - \lambda) > (1 - t)$ and $\lambda \odot \lambda < t$.

As $y_k \xrightarrow{(\tau,v,\eta)} y_*$, then for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we get $k_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\tau(y_k - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}) > 1 - \lambda$, $v(y_k - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda$ and $\eta(y_k - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda$ for $k \geq k_\epsilon$.

Now choose $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $k_0 \geq k_\epsilon$. Then, we have $\tau(y_{k_0} - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}) > 1 - \lambda$, $v(y_{k_0} - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda$ and $\eta(y_{k_0} - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda$. Again as $y = \{y_k\} \subseteq I_{(\tau, v, \eta)}^r(x)$, we have $y_{k_0} \in I_{(\tau, v, \eta)}^r(x)$. Then

$$\delta\left(\left\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, v\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda\right\}\right) > 0. \tag{4}$$

Choose $j \in \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) > 1 - \lambda, v(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda\}$, then we have $\tau(x_j - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) > 1 - \lambda$, $v(x_j - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda$ and $\eta(x_j - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}) < \lambda$.

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_j - y_*; r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau\left(x_j - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \otimes \tau\left(y_{k_0} - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &> (1 - \lambda) \otimes (1 - \lambda) \\ &> 1 - t, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(x_j - y_*; r + \epsilon) &\geq v\left(x_j - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \odot v\left(y_{k_0} - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &< \lambda \odot \lambda \\ &< t, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_j - y_*; r + \epsilon) &\geq \eta\left(x_j - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \odot \eta\left(y_{k_0} - y_*; \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) \\ &< \lambda \odot \lambda \\ &< t. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $j \in \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, v(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t\}$.

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} &\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, v\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda\} \\ &\subseteq \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, v(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t\}. \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} &\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) > 1 - \lambda, v\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta\left(x_k - y_{k_0}; r + \frac{\epsilon}{2}\right) < \lambda\}) \\ &\leq \delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, v(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t\}). \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Then using equation (4) and equation (5), we get

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, v(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - y_*; r + \epsilon) < t\}) > 0.$$

Therefore, $y_* \in I_{(\tau, v, \eta)}^r(x)$. \square

Theorem 2.15. Let $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$ be the set of all statistical cluster points with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) of sequence $x = \{x_k\}$ in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ and r be some non-negative real number. Then, for an arbitrary $\gamma \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we have $\varphi(\xi - \gamma; r) > 1 - \lambda$ and $\vartheta(\xi - \gamma; r) < \lambda$ for all $\xi \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x)$.

Proof. For $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ take $t \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) > 1 - \lambda$ and $t \odot t < \lambda$. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$. Then, for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $t \in (0, 1)$ we have

$$\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t\}) > 0. \quad (6)$$

Now we will show that if $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ have $\tau(\xi - \gamma; r) > 1 - t$, $\nu(\xi - \gamma; r) < t$ and $\eta(\xi - \gamma; r) < t$ then $\xi \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x)$.

Let $j \in \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t\}$, then $\tau(x_j - \gamma; \epsilon) > 1 - t$, $\nu(x_j - \gamma; \epsilon) < t$ and $\eta(x_j - \gamma; \epsilon) < t$. Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_j - \xi; r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau(x_j - \gamma; \epsilon) \otimes \tau(\xi - \gamma; r) \\ &> (1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) \\ &> 1 - \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(x_j - \xi; r + \epsilon) &\leq \nu(x_j - \gamma; \epsilon) \odot \nu(\xi - \gamma; r) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_j - \xi; r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta(x_j - \gamma; \epsilon) \odot \eta(\xi - \gamma; r) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

we have $\tau(x_j - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda$, $\nu(x_j - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda$ and $\eta(x_j - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda$. Thus $j \in \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda, \nu(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}$. Now the next inclusion holds.

$$\begin{aligned} &\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t\} \\ &\subseteq \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda, \nu(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \gamma; \epsilon) < t\}) \\ &\leq \delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda, \nu(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}). \end{aligned}$$

Using equation (6) we get $\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda, \nu(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}) > 0$. Therefore, $\xi \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x)$. \square

Theorem 2.16. If $\overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} = \{x \in \mathbb{X} : \varphi(x - c; r) \geq 1 - \lambda, \vartheta(x - c; r) \leq \lambda\}$ represents the closure of open ball $B(c, \lambda, r) = \{x \in \mathbb{X} : \varphi(x - c; r) > 1 - \lambda, \vartheta(x - c; r) < \lambda\}$ for some $r > 0$, $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and fixed $c \in \mathbb{X}$ then $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x) = \bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$.

Proof. For $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ take $t \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) > 1 - \lambda$ and $t \odot t < \lambda$. Let $\gamma \in \bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$ then there exists $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$ for some $r > 0$ and every $t \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$\tau(c - \gamma; r) > 1 - t, \nu(c - \gamma; r) < t \text{ and } \eta(c - \gamma; r) < t.$$

Fix $\epsilon > 0$. Since $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$ then we get $K = \{k \in \mathbb{X} : \tau(x_k - c; \epsilon) > 1 - t, \nu(x_k - c; \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - c; \epsilon) < t\}$ with $\delta(K) > 0$. Now, for $k \in K$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau(x_k - c; \epsilon) \otimes \tau(c - \gamma; r) \\ &> (1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) \\ &> 1 - \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) &\leq \nu(x_k - c; \epsilon) \odot \nu(c - \gamma; r) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta(x_k - c; \epsilon) \odot \eta(c - \gamma; r) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) > 1 - \lambda \text{ and } \vartheta(x_k - \gamma; r + \epsilon) < \lambda\}) > 0$. Hence, $\gamma \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x)$.

Therefore, $\bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} \subseteq \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x)$.

Conversely,

Let $\gamma \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x)$. For result, we will show that $\gamma \in \bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$.

Let if possible, $\gamma \notin \bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$ i.e. $\gamma \notin \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$ for all $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$.

Then $\tau(\gamma - c; r) \leq 1 - \lambda$ or $\nu(\gamma - c; r) \geq \lambda$, $\eta(\gamma - c; r) \geq \lambda$ for every $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$. By Theorem 2.15 for arbitrary $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$ we have $\tau(\gamma - c; r) > 1 - \lambda$, $\nu(\gamma - c; r) < \lambda$ and $\eta(\gamma - c; r) < \lambda$ for every $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)$ which leads to contradiction of our assumption.

Therefore, $\gamma \in \bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$. Hence, $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x) \subseteq \bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$. \square

Theorem 2.17. Let $x = \{x_k\}$ be any sequence in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ then for any $\lambda \in (0, 1)$,

(i) If $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x)$ then $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \subseteq \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$.

(ii) $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} = \{\xi \in \mathbb{X} : \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x) \subseteq \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}\}$.

Proof. (i) Let $\epsilon > 0$. For given $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ take $t \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) > 1 - \lambda$ and $t \odot t < \lambda$. Consider $\xi \in St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ and $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x)$.

Now for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $t \in (0, 1)$ consider sets

$$A = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi : r + \epsilon) > 1 - t, v(x_k - \xi : r + \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - \xi : r + \epsilon) < t\} \text{ with } \delta(A^c) = 0,$$

and

$$B = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - c; \epsilon) > 1 - t, v(x_k - c; \epsilon) < t \text{ and } \eta(x_k - c; \epsilon) < t\} \text{ with } \delta(B) \neq 0.$$

Now for $k \in A \cap B$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(\xi - c; r) &\geq \tau(x_k - c; \epsilon) \otimes \tau(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \\ &> (1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) \\ &> 1 - \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v(\xi - c; r) &\geq v(x_k - c; \epsilon) * v(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(\xi - c; r) &\geq \eta(x_k - c; \epsilon) * \eta(x_k - \xi; r + \epsilon) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\xi \in \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$. Hence, $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \subseteq \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$.

(ii) By previous part we have $St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \subseteq \bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{\varphi}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$.

Assume $y \in \bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$ then $\tau(y - c; r) \geq 1 - \lambda$, $v(y - c; r) \leq \lambda$ and $\eta(y - c; r) \leq \lambda$ for

all $c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x)$. This implies that $\Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x) \subseteq \overline{B(y, \lambda, r)}$, i.e. $\bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} \subseteq \{\xi \in$

$\mathbb{X} : \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x) \subseteq \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}\}$.

Further, let $y \notin St_{(\tau, v, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ then for $\epsilon > 0$ we have $\delta(\{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - y; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda$ or $v(x_k - y; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda$, $\eta(x_k - y; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda\}) \neq 0$, which implies that a statistical cluster point c exists for $x = \{x_k\}$ with $\tau(y - c; r + \epsilon) \leq 1 - \lambda$, $v(y - c; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda$ or $\eta(y - c; r + \epsilon) \geq \lambda$.

Thus, $\Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x) \not\subseteq \overline{B(y, \lambda, r)}$ and $y \notin \{\xi \in \mathbb{X} : \Gamma_{(\tau, v, \eta)}(x) \subseteq \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}\}$. This implies

that $\{\xi \in \mathbb{X} : \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x) \subseteq \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}\} \subseteq St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ and we get $\bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} \subseteq St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$.

Therefore, $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} = \{\xi \in \mathbb{X} : \Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x) \subseteq \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}\}$. \square

Theorem 2.18. *Let $x = \{x_k\}$ be any sequence in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ which is statistically convergent to $\xi \in \mathbb{X}$ with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) then there exists $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ such that $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}$ for some $r > 0$.*

Proof. Let $\epsilon > 0$. For given $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ take $t \in (0, 1)$ with $(1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) > 1 - \lambda$ and $t \odot t < \lambda$. Since $x_k \xrightarrow{St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \xi$ then there is a set $A = \{k \in \mathbb{N} : \tau(x_k - \xi; \epsilon) \leq 1 - t \text{ or } \nu(x_k - \xi; \epsilon) \geq t, \eta(x_k - \xi; \epsilon) \geq t\}$ with $\delta(A) = 0$. Consider $y \in \overline{B(\xi, t, r)} = \{y \in \mathbb{X} : \tau(y - \xi; r) \geq 1 - t, \nu(y - \xi; r) \leq t, \eta(y - \xi; r) \leq t\}$.

For $k \in A^c$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x_k - y; r + \epsilon) &\geq \tau(x_k - \xi; \epsilon) \otimes \tau(y - \xi; r) \\ &> (1 - t) \otimes (1 - t) \\ &> 1 - \lambda, \\ \nu(x_k - y; r + \epsilon) &\leq \nu(x_k - \xi; \epsilon) \odot \nu(y - \xi; r) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \eta(x_k - y; r + \epsilon) &\leq \eta(x_k - \xi; \epsilon) \odot \eta(y - \xi; r) \\ &< t \odot t \\ &< \lambda. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $y \in St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$, i.e. $\overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)} \subseteq St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$. Also $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r \subseteq \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}$. Hence, $St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r = \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}$. \square

Theorem 2.19. *Let $x = \{x_k\}$ be any sequence in a NNS $(\mathbb{X}, \mathfrak{N}, \otimes, \odot)$ which converges statistically with respect to neutrosophic norm (τ, ν, η) then $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x) = St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$ for some $r > 0$.*

Proof. Necessary part:

Suppose $x_k \xrightarrow{St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}} \xi$. Then $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}(x) = \{\xi\}$. By Theorem 2.16 for some $r > 0$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ we have $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x) = \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}$. Also by Theorem 2.18 we get $\overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)} = St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$. Hence, $\Gamma_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}^r(x) = St_{(\tau, \nu, \eta)}-LIM_x^r$.

Sufficient part:

Let $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}^r(x) = St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r$. By using Theorem 2.16 and Theorem 2.17(ii) we get

$$\bigcup_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} = \bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)}$$

. This implies that either $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x) = \phi$ or $\Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x)$ is a singleton set. Then $St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r =$

$\bigcap_{c \in \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x)} \overline{B(c, \lambda, r)} = \overline{B(\xi, \lambda, r)}$ for some $\xi \in \Gamma_{(\tau,v,\eta)}(x)$, further by Theorem 2.18 we get

$$St_{(\tau,v,\eta)}-LIM_x^r = \{\xi\}. \quad \square$$

3. Conclusion

We have introduced the considerable convergence structure called rough statistical convergence on neutrosophic normed spaces. As neutrosophic set is an effective tools to control the inconsistent and indeterminate data, also the theory of rough convergence is a powerful mathematical technique for dealing the convergence problems with present incompleteness in data. The computational techniques with these structures may not always sufficient to produce the best results alone although the merging of two or more of them can provide much improved results. Thus, the significance of introducing rough convergence in this structure is that resultant computational techniques will give a novel mathematical tool to deal with the convergence problems that have been motivated on the basis of practical approach by factual incompleteness, indeterminacy and inconsistency of the data. Moreover, rough statistical convergence on neutrosophic normed spaces can be explored for the different setups like double sequences, triple sequences, ideals, difference sequences and many more.

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